

THE IMAGE OF A JUST RULER

Gullola Haydarova

Teacher of Uzbek Language and Literature,
Fergana Academic Lyceum of the Ministry of Internal
Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan
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Abstract

The article discusses the artistic interpretation of the ideas of humanity, social justice, and patriotism promoted by Alisher Navoi through the image of Iskandar.

Key words: historical figure, artistic interpretation, personal qualities, social justice, universal human ideas, educational characteristics.

When Alisher Navoi set out to create the epic poem “*Saddi Iskandariy*”, he aimed not only to depict the military prowess of this historical figure, but also to focus on his human qualities and his system of just governance. This intention is especially evident in Iskandar’s words spoken when he is offered the throne after his father’s death. Addressing the people, he openly admits that he is no better than others and that he also has weaknesses:

*I am no better than you, rather in many ways inferior,
Fatherless, with a wounded heart, helpless...*

After this, the author of the epic, speaking through Iskandar, generalizes the views of his contemporaries on a just ruler, explains what the “father of the nation” should be like, and outlines the requirements placed upon the ideal ruler in medieval thought:

*Now choose a king for yourselves,
Find a protector for this land.
In every matter superior to the people of his time,
So that he may be worthy of kingship.*

The theme of justice and fairness, which is one of the leading ideas in almost all epics of the “*Khamsa*”, also finds its epic expression in “*Saddi Iskandariy*”. Indeed, peace among the people and prosperity of the country are ensured through justice:

*Justice is like the season of Navruz,
In governance it shines like lightning across the world.*

Accordingly, in the following lines spoken by Iskandar, the author’s call to learn lessons from history and to be compassionate toward the people is also reflected:

Be firm against the enemy in times of need,

*Be gentle and kind toward the people.
Make the throne and power his dwelling,
Adorn his head with crown and honor.*

The concepts of truth and justice are harmonized in Navoi's works. Following God's commandments, adhering to truth, and supporting those who do not shy away from speaking the truth should be the primary principles of a ruler's policy. Only then will the hands of oppressors be restrained, and peace will come to the people:

*Following what God has commanded,
Let the people firmly hold to the truth.
May oppression be worn away,
And peace be delivered to the people.*

After the proclamation of such a noble program of governance and lofty goals, everyone rejoices and repeatedly asks Iskandar to become king. Finally, Iskandar agrees and urges the people to treat him not as a distant ruler adorned with crown and throne, but as a close and compassionate person. He calls on them to see the throne and crown not as symbols of fear and terror, but as means to realize goodness and justice. He wishes that anyone who comes before him with a complaint should feel as if they are facing a kind and understanding friend rather than a powerful and wrathful king:

*When one comes to present their plea before me,
Let them think of me as one of their own.
Let my throne cause them no fear,
Let my crown inspire no terror.
Let my title of king not distress them,
Nor make them rush anxiously to state their plea.*

Iskandar remains faithful to his promises and devotes himself day and night to justice, the people, and the affairs of the country. As a result, before long the land becomes prosperous and the people happy:

*All kinds of deeds in his father's time
That had caused suffering to the people,
He removed entirely from their lives,
So that benefit might reach the people.*

Precisely because Iskandar was surrounded by unparalleled scholars—wise, knowledgeable, and sincere friends—listened to their sound advice, acted justly, stood alongside the people, responded to their cries, and sought their interests, he never faced defeat in any land or matter. His authority and power

grew ever stronger, and he conquered the world in pursuit of the noblest goals. Thus, he fulfilled Navoi's highest humanistic ideal expressed in the following lines:

*With justice, make the face of the world prosperous,
With good character, make the people of the world joyful.*

When we examine the artistic expression of historical information in "*Saddi Iskandariy*", we come to understand how closely Navoi's artistic interpretation aligns with historical truth. The poet himself emphasized, before beginning his epics, that he had "searched through many old records." Even in his historical works, we see that he carefully studied previous sources, selecting the most objective facts. The information presented through the example of Iskandar clearly confirms this.

Alisher Navoi emphasizes that a ruler must be fully mature and knowledgeable, illustrating this through the image of Iskandar. He also addresses this issue specifically in "*Tarixi Muluki Ajam*", stating: "Four hundred scholars served him. Plato the Divine was his leader, and he had Aristotle as his vizier..." The great poet and thinker also draws wisdom from the events surrounding Iskandar's death, offering instructive conclusions for those devoted to accumulating wealth and those who distance themselves from good and charitable deeds. The legend that Iskandar willed his empty hands to be left outside his coffin gains even greater emotional significance through Navoi's pen:

"It is said that he made a will that his bare hands be left outside the coffin, so that it would serve as a warning and lesson to the people of the world, reminding them that one leaves this world empty-handed."

Conclusion

In conclusion, Alisher Navoi not only portrays his hero's military courage and fame, but also seeks to instill in the reader's heart his human qualities, devotion to the people, and patriotism. Through this, he enriches moral and spiritual understanding—and succeeds fully in this aim

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